

Emerging Markets and International Portfolio Optimization

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Abstract

In this paper we studied the impact of the integration of emerging markets in a portfolio composed initially of developed markets. The sample is composed of seven stock indices of developed markets and nine emerging market stock indices. Our main conclusions are the following. First, a study of the whole horizon showed that efficient frontier composed of developed and emerging markets dominates the efficient frontier composed of developed markets. Second, a more detailed study of efficient frontier on different sub-periods showed that the interest of emerging markets fluctuates over time. This, was approved by BOX'M test which showed instability of the parameters involved in the optimization strategy.

Key words: Emerging markets, Portfolio optimization, Markowitz model, Efficient frontier

JEL codes: G11, G15

1. Introduction

The development of emerging markets has formed a major financial event since the end of the Cold War. An unprecedented growth of these markets marked this period. Improved macro-economic outlook for emerging countries associated with massive capital inflows in the early 90s, led to spectacular increases. In these conditions, emergent markets have attracted increasing interest of Western investors. Thus, the inclusion of emerging market assets in an international portfolio seemed to be a profitable strategy.

Building a portfolio from investments is one of the most important financial decisions which face an investor or an institution. The process of decision making should be developed to identify appropriate allocation of each investment in the portfolio. The portfolio must correspond to the expectations of the investor in terms of trade-off between risk and return.

The first who incorporated an emerging market in a strategy of international diversification was Grubel (1968), his approach was then adopted and developed by several authors, namely Lessard (1973), Levy and Sarnat (1970) and especially Errunza (1977), focusing on the merits of emerging markets given their ability to generate important diversification potentials compared to the developed markets.

In this paper we will focus on evaluating the impact of the integration of emerging markets in a global portfolio. We will therefore, as a first step study the correlations. We then move on to the study of the displacement of the efficient frontier when integrating emerging markets in an international portfolio. This allows us to show the variability of the advantage offered by these markets, namely the reduction of risk on the different sub-periods. This study of the efficient frontier

will be complemented by statistical tests showing the instability of the parameters involved in the elaboration of the diversification strategy.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 is devoted to review of related literature. The data and methodology are presented in Section 3. The results are presented in Section 4. Section 5 provided conclusions.

2. Review of Related Literature

The portfolio selection problem is of interest theoretical as well as practical. Markowitz (1952) was the pioneer of this line of research after the implementation of mean-variance model. The study of Markowitz has solved the problem of portfolio selection in an intuitive manner; his technique known by mean-variance analysis is based on the trade-off faced by an investor: risk against return. A portfolio is said to be efficient if it generates a maximum mean given a certain level of risk or a minimum variance for a given value of mean. The investor chooses among the set of efficient portfolios, called efficient frontier, the appropriate portfolio according to his preference for risk and return. The idea is simple, intuitive and attractive, and the technique requires only a simple procedure of maximization, in addition, only historical asset returns are used to estimate the efficient frontier.

Thus, and starting with the problem of portfolio choice, several articles have been published highlighting the merits of emerging markets in an international diversification strategy.

Errunza (1977) studied quarterly returns excluding dividends of stock market indices of 29 Countries, for a period that extends from 1957 to 1971.

According to this study, the returns of less developed and semi developed countries during this period are not higher than those of developed countries, but what makes them interesting is their low correlation with other stocks exchanges, from where their importance in the composition of the portfolio. This therefore, justifies their admission into optimal portfolios, although their respective risk-return performance is not among the best.

Errunza therefore, concluded the need for an international diversification including the emergent markets.

Divecha, Drak and Stefek (DDS) (1992) were also been interested in emerging markets. Their database included monthly data converted into dollars from February 1986 to March 1991 for 23 emerging countries and 20 developed countries. DDS came to the conclusion that emerging markets are weakly correlated with each other and also with the developed markets, which constitutes the feature of these countries, allowing reducing the global portfolio risk and generating subsequently, diversification gains. (DDS) (1992) have traced the efficient frontier from IFC and Financial Times indices, and showed that the integration of emerging countries to a proportion of 20% in the overall portfolio reduces its risk and this even if the expected returns in emerging markets are not higher than those of developed markets.

Speidell and Sappenfield (1992) have noted from their study based on 18 emerging markets and 18 developed markets that the correlation between developed markets increases as a result of international global events, while the impact of these events is less strong on emergent countries and is even negative in some of these markets. This means that, in the case of an international financial crisis, the isolation of these markets allows them to fulfill perfectly their role of risk diversification, hence, the need to integrate these countries into a global portfolio given their low correlation between them and with developed markets.

Diwan Errunza, Senbet (DES) (1994) traced the efficient frontier constructed from three possible universes: developed markets, emerging markets and a combination of both. They showed that an American investor, who invested passively in the SP500 index, improves his performance by placing abroad, since this portfolio is dominated, in ascending order, by the efficient frontier of the developed markets and then emerging markets and finally of global market.

Harvey (1991) compared the performance of passive and active strategy for American investors over the period 1970-1989. His approach was to examine the efficient frontier using the Markowitz mean-variance optimization. Harvey (1991) found that investment diversification across markets reduced overall risk portfolio while enhancing its profitability. Thus, a passive international diversification is less risky than an American portfolio and provides the double of the performance of a domestic American portfolio.

Harvey (1995b) repeated the same approach proposed by Diwan Errunza, Senbet (DES) (1994), by plotting the efficient frontier calculated from 18 industrialized countries (Morgan Stanley Capital International), then adding 19 emergent countries. The second curve clearly dominates in terms of performance and especially risk the first, showing the interest of emerging markets. In a second step, Harvey (1995b) repeated this process by prohibiting short selling. This restriction seems necessary, to the extent that, the level of liquidity and sophistication of emerging markets rarely allows the practice of short selling. This modification does not significantly change the results.

Harvey (1995b) subsequently, developed a statistical test to confirm that the displacement of the efficient frontier is significant and is not the result of a chance sampling. Finally, the author developed a strategy that consists of choosing monthly a minimum variance portfolio, established from historical data for the past five years. The period runs from March 1981 to June 1992. In a first step, only developed markets are considered. Then, this strategy is applied including emerging markets in the universe of potential assets. This second configuration provides a slightly better performance, but especially a lower risk.

Harvey concluded that the main interest of the emerging markets for a portfolio manager lies not in increasing returns, but in decreasing risk.

Thus, all these aforementioned studies have shown the interest of emerging markets in the context of international portfolio management, due to their diversification potential which reduces the risk.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data used in the study

Our analysis focuses on nine emerging stock markets namely, Egypt, Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, Turkey, Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan and Korea, and seven developed markets: Germany, Canada, France, Italy, Japan, Great Britain and the United States and covers a period ranging from December 2002 to December 2008. The data in this study consists on monthly series of international indices expressed in U.S. dollars as follows:

- For emerging markets : CMA (Egypt), le MerVal (Argentina), le Bovespa (Brazil), le IPC (Mexico), le ISE National 100 (Turkey), le KLSE composite (Malaysia), le Straits Times (Singapore), le TW 11 (Taiwan), le Seoul composite (Korea).
- For developed markets : DAX (Germany), S & P TSX Composite (Canada), CAC 40 (France), AS MIB (Italy), Nikkei 225 (Japan), FTSE 100 (G. Britain), S & P 500 (USA)

3.2 Methodology

Our goal in this paper is to examine whether it is appropriate for an American investor to invest a portion of the portfolio in emerging markets indices.

Monthly returns of stock indices are calculated using the following formula:

$$R_t = \frac{I_t - I_{t-1}}{I_{t-1}} \quad R_t : \text{monthly returns}$$

I_t : the index at the instant t (month t)

I_{t-1} : the index at the instant t-1 (month t)

In a first step, a diagnosis of emerging and developed markets returns is established to determine the characteristics of these markets through a normality test by analyzing the coefficients of skewness (S) and kurtosis (K):

$$S = \frac{1/n \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^3}{\left[1/n \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2\right]^{3/2}} \quad K = \frac{1/n \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^4}{\left[1/n \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2\right]^2} \quad (1)$$

In order to better decide on the interest of emerging markets, we analyzed the correlations between emerging markets, between developed markets and between emerging and developed markets.

To make the study closer to reality, we calculated the optimal weights that an American investor would allocate to emerging and developed market in order to build an international portfolio optimally diversified. Subsequently, we examined the impact of emerging markets on the efficient frontier. For this, we considered two possible universes. The first consisting only of developed markets, this universe is denoted D (containing seven markets), the second representing the combination of both emerging and developed markets, is denoted D + E (containing seven developed markets 9 and emerging markets). The analysis is conducted first, on the whole study period namely from December 2002 to December 2008. Then, three sub-periods will be considered: décembre2002 – décembre2004, décembre2004 – décembre2006, décembre2006 – décembre2008.

For each considered period of analysis, we varied marginally a target return level for a global minimum variance portfolio. All combinations that offer a minimum of risk for a given level of return constitute the efficient frontier. Each point on the frontier represents a specific portfolio different from others by its composition, that is to say, by the weights allocated to each emerging or developed market.

Markowitz algorithm allowed us to determine optimal weights:

$$\text{Min} \sum_i \sum_j X_i X_j \text{Cov}(R_i, R_j) \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_i X_i E(R_i) = R^*$$

$$\sum_i X_i = 1$$

$X_i > 0$ X_i : The optimal weight to allocate

These efficient frontiers obtained from historical returns are analyzed by turn, to determine whether international diversification turned towards emerging markets can reach a better level of risk (minimum risk) for the same level of return.

The elaboration of Box'M test allowed us to test the stability of the correlation matrix, therefore, the stability of the parameters involved in the diversification strategy. Thus, the period was divided into three sub-periods: the first lies between December 2002 and December 2004, the second between December 2004 and December 2006, and finally the last between December 2006 and December 2008. For each of them, the correlation matrix was calculated as well as Box's M test for testing the equality of correlation matrix.

H_0 : : equality of correlation matrix
 H_1 : : inequality of correlation matrix

4. Empirical results

4.1 Diagnostic of returns of emerging and developed markets

Table 1 shows the average monthly returns and standard deviations of stock indices of nine emerging countries and seven developed countries for the period from December 2002 to December 2008.

For emerging market, average monthly returns, vary between (-0.82%) for Taiwan and (4.44%) for Turkey. The majority of studied emerging markets show higher returns than the U.S. index in particular and then indices of the G7 countries in general which range from (-0.83%) for Japan to (1%) for Italy. However, it should be noted that, the returns of all emerging markets are much more volatile than developed markets, with a standard deviation of (19.98%) for Turkey, (13.57%) for Argentine etc ... except for Egypt whose standard deviation is low and is of the order of (3.49%).

Unlike the emerging markets, developed markets present much lower standard deviations, all lower than 8%. Emerging markets offer therefore, high returns but also high volatility showing a greater instability.

Table1: Monthly returns

	<i>Average return</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
<i>Emerging markets</i>				
Turkey	4,44%	19,98%	1,315	4,423
Egypt	1,05%	3,49%	1,338	3,466
Korea	0,62%	13,36%	1,006	2,537
Malaysia	-6,33 E-03%	10,18%	0,636	1,738
Singapore	0,21%	9,15%	0,561	1,652
Taiwan	0,82%	9,29%	0,575	1,299
Argentina	0,78%	13,57%	0,876	4,224
Brazil	1,82%	11,21%	-0,701	1,278
Mexico	1,33%	8,61%	-0,406	0,722
<i>Developed Markets</i>				
Germany	0,51%	7,55%	-0,707	1,117
Canada	0,55%	5,34%	-0,793	1,837
France	0,81%	6,6%	-0,454	-0,078
Italy	1%	7,44%	0,458	0,487
Japan	-0,83%	5,73%	0,140	-0,924
G. Britain	0,17%	4,36%	-0,519	0,157
USA	0,56%	5,08%	-0,477	-0,220

4.1.1 Normality test

Table 1 also shows the skewness and kurtosis coefficients of all countries. These coefficients are used to detect normality of series by comparing them to those of normal distribution, knowing that for a normal distribution the skewness is zero and kurtosis is 3.

Most of the emerging markets are characterized by Non-normal distributions. Indeed, returns are skewed to the right especially for Turkey (1,315), Egypt (1,338), and Korea (1,006). The right asymmetry is an argument in favor of emerging markets to the extent that, it indicates, relative to a normal distribution, a higher probability of realization of returns higher than the average return. On the contrary, developed markets have much more symmetrical returns relative to the average return (all skewness coefficients less than 1.).

Regarding the coefficients of kurtosis, they are high for some emerging markets namely (4.423) for Turkey (4,224) for Argentina (3,466) for Egypt. The distribution is thus called leptokurtic, expressing a high frequency of realization of extreme returns in these markets.

4.2 The study of correlation

The most advanced argument in favor of emerging markets lies in their low correlations between themselves or with the developed markets.

Table 2: Correlations between emergent markets

	<i>Turkey</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Korea</i>	<i>Malaysia</i>	<i>Singapore</i>	<i>Taiwan</i>	<i>Argentina</i>	<i>Brazil</i>	<i>Mexico</i>
<i>Turkey</i>	1,000								
<i>Egypt</i>	0,185	1,000							
<i>Korea</i>	0,192	0,162	1,000						
<i>Malaysia</i>	0,057	0,282	0,349	1,000					
<i>Singapore</i>	0,213	0,193	0,433	0,629	1,000				
<i>Taiwan</i>	0,264	0,230	0,422	0,458	0,469	1,000			
<i>Argentina</i>	0,189	0,084	0,294	0,388	0,531	0,572	1,000		
<i>Brazil</i>	0,318	0,313	0,341	0,347	0,571	0,480	0,415	1,000	
<i>Mexico</i>	0,276	0,219	0,326	0,432	0,643	0,461	0,567	0,674	1,000

The above table presents the correlations between emerging markets. We note that these markets are weakly correlated with each other. Indeed, the correlations are of the order of (0.084) for Argentina and Egypt and (0.057) for Turkey and Malaysia...

Table 3: Correlations between developed markets

	<i>Germany</i>	<i>Canada</i>	<i>France</i>	<i>Italy</i>	<i>Japan</i>	<i>G. Britain</i>	<i>USA</i>
<i>Germany</i>	1,000						
<i>Canada</i>	0,631	1,000					
<i>France</i>	0,881	0,648	1,000				
<i>Italy</i>	0,708	0,570	0,824	1,000			
<i>Japan</i>	0,452	0,488	0,465	0,397	1,000		
<i>G. Britain</i>	0,793	0,672	0,794	0,691	0,408	1,000	
<i>USA</i>	0,771	0,795	0,745	0,587	0,504	0,812	1,000

Table 3 presents the correlations between the different countries of G7, they are quite strong. We note a significant correlation between Germany and France (88.1%) and especially between European countries in general, confirming the importance of financial flows and commercial exchange between these countries. Similarly, the high correlation between Canada and the USA (79.5%) reflects the economic and financial integration of the two countries.

Table 4: Correlations between developed and emergent markets

	Germany	Canada	France	Italy	Japan	G. Britain	USA
Turkey	0,398	0,339	0,403	0,370	,301	0,417	0,305
Egypt	0,060	0,279	0,174	0,206	,0154	0,179	0,188
Korea	0,318	0,370	0,320	0,291	0,508	0,461	0,416
Malaysia	0,299	0,443	0,268	0,217	0,195	0,322	0,384
Singapore	0,422	0,559	0,444	0,334	0,375	0,528	0,577
Taiwan	0,413	0,368	0,345	0,310	0,345	0,369	0,399
Argentina	0,314	0,426	0,248	0,289	0,180	0,279	0,302
Brazil	0,603	0,655	0,625	0,549	0,534	0,637	0,644
Mexico	0,522	0,691	0,478	0,458	0,371	0,563	0,657

The Table 4 shows that, the correlations between indices returns of emerging and developed markets are relatively low, it is of (6%) between Egypt and Germany. Similarly, the correlation between American market and different emerging markets is low, except for Brazil (64.4%), Singapore (57.7%) and Mexico (65.7%). Thus, the low correlation between emerging and developed markets associated with a strong correlation between the nine developed markets, makes attractive the strategy of international diversification of portfolios of American investors towards emerging markets rather than developed markets.

4.3 Impact of emerging markets on the international portfolio: Study of the efficient frontier

4.3.1 Analysis of the efficiency frontier over the whole study period from 2002 to 2008

The Figure 1 below shows the efficient frontier based on historical returns for the period 2002- 2008:

Figure 1: Efficient frontier over the period 2002-2008

We note from the graph, that efficient frontier (D + E) representing the combination of developed and emerging markets, dominates the efficient frontier (D) representing the developed markets only. Indeed, for the same level of return, the efficient frontier representing combination of the two markets is situated below that limited to developed markets. Similarly, the efficient portfolios composing (D + E), represent for the same level of return, risks (variance) significantly lower than that composing the efficient frontier (D). Thus, for a given level of return equal to 0.3%, the variance of the portfolio decreases from 0.139% for (D), to 0.0442% (D + E). So, we can conclude from this first study, that the integration of emerging markets in the universe of investments, improves the performance of international portfolio. For an American investor the integration of emerging markets in the global portfolio would have allowed during this period, to reach lower levels of risk for a given level of return. These markets seem to be of interest.

4.3.2 Analysis of the efficient frontier over different sub-periods

Figure 2: Efficient frontier over the period 2006-2008

From the graph, we note that over the period 2006-2008, the efficient frontier including emerging markets indices, has largely dominated in terms of the variance, the efficient frontier of developed market. Indeed, the efficient frontier (D + E) is located entirely below the efficient frontier (D). For the same return equal to 0.5%, the variance of the portfolio belonging to (D + E) is equal to 0.02535%, while the variance of the portfolio belonging to (D) is equal to 0.176%. The integration of emerging markets in global portfolio seems to be advantageous for the period 2006-2008.

Figure3: Efficient frontier over the period 2002-2004:

We note that, the integration of emerging markets improves the performance of the international portfolio. However, this improvement is absent for levels of returns above 3%. Indeed, we note that from this level of return, efficient frontiers are superimposed presenting both, portfolios with the same risk (even minimum variance) equal to 0.6%. Thus, the weakness of diversification potential seems to reduce the interest of emerging markets in the period 2002-2004.

Figure 4: Efficient frontier over the period: 2004-2006

For levels of returns below 2.5%, we note that efficient frontier (D + E), is situated below the efficient frontier (D). But we can also note that, from level of return above 2.5%, the integration of emerging markets in global portfolio seems to present a problem, to the extent that, they no longer allow a lower risk but rather an increase of it. Indeed, for a return of 3%, the minimum variance portfolio located on the efficient frontier (D + E), presents a risk of 0.559%, while portfolio located on the efficient frontier (D), has a lower risk of about 0.2%. Therefore, in this case, integrating emerging markets in international diversification seems to be a non profitable strategy.

The previous study carried on the efficient frontier, on different periods, leads us to conclude that at certain periods, emerging markets allow a significant reduction of risk (2006-2008), at others they do not change the diversification potential (2002-2004), their integration into the global portfolio may even cause a significant augmentation of risk (2004-2006). Therefore, the attractiveness of emerging markets seems to vary according to periods.

The study of efficient frontier in different periods seems to indicate instability of the parameters involved in the diversification strategy, in other words, the instability of correlations between different financial markets. We will therefore, in the following try to analyze the stabilities of these parameters.

4.4 Stability of the correlation matrix

According to test 1 studying equality of correlation matrix between developed and emerging markets in different periods, we note that the stability of correlation matrix is rejected. Indeed, and according the Box'M test, there is no equality, for example, between the correlation matrix calculated for the period (2002-2004) and the correlation matrix calculated for the period (2004-2006) with a degree of significance less than 5% and therefore reject of H0. This remains valid for other sub-periods according to Box'M test, the degree of significance is less than 5%.

Test 1

(2002-2004) - (2004-2006)

Test Results

Box's M		295,999
F	Approx.	1,460
	df 1	136
	df 2	6885,570
	Sig.	,000

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2002-2004)-(2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		618,963
F	Approx.	1,585
	df 1	272
	df 2	13503,532
	Sig.	,000

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2004-2006)-(2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		312,808
F	Approx.	1,427
	df 1	136
	df 2	6436,315
	Sig.	,001

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

Test 2

(2002-2004)- (2004-2006)

Test Results

Box's M		41,268
F	Approx.	1,268
	df 1	28
	df 2	8531,266
	Sig.	,156

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2002-2004)-(2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		124,899
F	Approx.	1,942
	df 1	56
	df 2	15499,800
	Sig.	,000

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2004-2006)- (2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		68,651
F	Approx.	2,058
	df 1	28
	df 2	7668,788
	Sig.	,001

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

Test 3

Test Results

Box's M		117,297
F	Approx.	2,140
	df 1	45
	df 2	8069,102
	Sig.	,000

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2002-2004)-(2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		245,190
F	Approx.	2,272
	df 1	90
	df 2	14890,807
	Sig.	,000

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

(2004-2006) -(2006-2008)

Test Results

Box's M		100,434
F	Approx.	1,771
	df 1	45
	df 2	7230,322
	Sig.	,001

Tests null hypothesis of equal population covariance matrices.

We note that, when all countries are included in the correlation matrix, its stability on all sub-periods is clearly rejected. However, when the developed countries and emerging countries are separated, the rejection of equality hypothesis of the correlation matrix is less categorical. Indeed, we note that the correlation matrix of the developed countries is relatively stable for the periods (2002-2004) - (2004-2006) with a degree of significance greater than 5% (15.6%).

It seems therefore, that the instability comes largely from the correlation between developed and emerging markets and from the correlation between emerging markets. This finding, calls into question the benefits offered by emerging markets since they do not always present a significant diversification potential, and their overall level of risk is high in the presence of a correlation.

5. Conclusion

Our goal in this paper was to evaluate the interest offered by emerging markets in an international portfolio management. The normality test showed that these markets are characterized by high returns but also high volatility. Correlations came approve the advantage offered by these markets to the extent that, the results found showed a weak correlation between these markets as well as with developed markets.

Similarly, the study of the efficient frontier which covered the period from December 2002 to December 2008, focused on indices of seven developed markets and 9 emerging markets, showed that the performance of the international portfolio has markedly improved, when the American investor introduces emerging market indices in his portfolio. This improvement came particularly of the reduction of total portfolio risk.

A more detailed analysis of the efficient frontier on different sub-periods showed that the interest of these markets significantly fluctuates over time. Indeed, the integration of these markets seems, on some sub-periods, not changing the diversification potential and allows even a significant increase in the risk on the others. This finding was confirmed by the statistical tests which have markedly rejected the stability of the correlation matrix.

Although these markets offer permanently investment opportunities, this result calls into question the argument that emerging markets would be interesting in a risk diversification strategy. Their benefits remain more or less strong depending on the period.

However, the results presented in this study are in part dependent on the definition chosen of risk, i.e., the variability of market returns, other definitions of risk as the maximum loss amount can lead to different results. The transaction cost usually high in these markets, the access to information, etc., are all elements which tend to nuance the results.

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